

TIL VA INTERNET

Rustamova Diyora Ulug'bek qizi

Buxoro davlat universitetining Pedagogika instituti talabasi

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ANNOTATSIYA: Internet bugungi kunda insonlarning juda muhim vositasiga aylangan, internet shunday bir muloqot muhiti, tilni amalga oshirishning alohida bir joyi hisoblanadiki, buning o'tmishda o'xshashi bo'lmagan. Internet muhitida muloqot jarayonida tabiiy tildan foydalanish lingvistik tizimli muhim aloqa tahlilining obyektiga aylanishi kerak.

Kalit so'zlar: Internet, til, global tarmoq kommunikatsiyalari, WEBLISH, SMS muloqoti, UNICODE tizimi.

Dunyoda inson zoti yaratilibdiki, bir-biri bilan gaplashadi ,so'zlashadi, o'zaro muomalada bo'ladi. Bunda tilning o'rne beqiyos, albatta. Inson til orqali boshqa tirik mavjudotlardan ongli ravishda farq qiladi. Dunyoda tillar juda ham ko'p bo'lib, ammo har bir millat, xalqning, o'z sevimli tili mavjud va ular shu tilda bemalol muloqot qila oladi. Ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, dunyoda 6 mingdan ortiq til mavjud bo'lib, ularning 90 % yo'qolish arafasida. Bu ko'rsatkich asosan kam sonli millat tilida uchraydi.

Internet bu hozirgi zamon talabidagi yagona ommabop kompyuter tarmog'i hisoblanib, bizga barcha sohalarga oid noaniqlik ya'ni ongimizga mavhum bo'lgan tushunchalar haqida ochiq, oddiy va ravon ma'lumot beruvchi axborot manbaidir. Tabiiyki, hozirgi kunda ushbu omilga bo'lgan ehtiyoj kundan kunga oshib bormoqda. Mazkur tarmoq butun dunyo miqyosida global tarmoq hisoblanadi. Internet tili juda murakkab va serqirrali hisoblanadi. Chunki internet tarmoqlarida tilning ya'ni nutqning barcha uslublarga xos materiallar insonlar uchun xizmat qilmoqda. Internetning asosiy vazifasi kommunikativlikdir.

Darhaqiqat, global tarmoq kommunikatsiyaning umumiy ma'nodagi samarali vositasi bo'lib, u hududiy jihatidan bir-biridan olisda bo'lgan insonlarning muloqot qilishga yordam beradi. Shu bilan bir qatorda insternet tili ta'siriga esa vosita ham hisoblanib, unng yordamida ma'lum bir g'oyaviy, tijoriy va siyosiy maqsadlarni amalga oshirish uchun ishontiriladi, dalil

keltiriladi, targ'ib qilinadi. Keyingi o'n yillikda atrofimizdagi olam tubdan o'zgardi. Kompyuterlar va mobil aloqalar insonning kundalik ehtiyojiga aylandi.

Zamonaviy jamiyat globallashuv davriga qadam qo'ydi. Jadal rivojlanib borayotgan axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari zamonaviy kommunikatsiya madaniyatini asosiy shakllantiruvchi vosita sifatida internet orqali muloqotga o'rganuvchi tilshunos-lingvistlar e'tiborini tortmoqda. XX asrning oxirida ingliz tilshunosligida hatto maxsus – computer-mediated communication (kompyuterli-kommunikatsiya) atamasi paydo bo'ldi. Ingliz neologizmida “netizen” so'zi “Internet” so'zidan kelib chiqib, “citezen” ya'ni ba'zan kun-u tun doimiy bo'sh vaqtini mazkur tarmoqqa bag'ishlaydigan “Internet mamlakatining doimiy aholisi” ma'nosini anglatadi. Lingvistik innovatsiyalar orasida ko'plab abbreviatura va qisqartma so'zlar mavjud. Hozirgi davrda tarmoqning faol foydalanuvchilari uchun ingliz tilining WEBLISH shakli yuzaga kelgan. Bunday o'zgarishlar SMS-muloqotda ham keng qo'llanilmoqda. Qisqartma sozlar o'zbek tilini ham chetlab o'tmadi. O'zbek tilidagi SMS-qisqartmalar variantlaridan ayrimlarini quyida ko'rib chiqish mumkin:

- Un,u-n,u/n= uchun
- Ln Bn, b-n,b/n= bilan
- = Lekin
- Kk= Kerak
- Bb= Bo'lib
- Db= Deb
- H= Ha
- Yo= Yo'q
- 'W' esa – Sh – harfining o'rniga qo'llaniladi.
- /belgisi “-lar” – qo'shimchasining o'rniga qo'llaniladi.
- = belgisi “ning” – qo'shimchasining o'rniga qo'llaniladi.
- “9” raqami ‘ya’ – harfining o'rniga qo'llaniladi.
- ‘6’ raqami “o” –harfining o'rnida qo'llaniladi.

Taniqli Britaniya tilshunos olimi Devid Kristal o'zining Internet va tilning o'zaro ta'siri muammolariga bag'ishlangan ilmiy tadqiqotda til to'g'risidagi “Twenty-first century English”

asarida o'qituvchilar tilni ilgari va hozirgi holatini o'rganish imkoniyatiga ekanliklarini ta'kidlaydi. Shuningdek, o'qituvchilar kelajakda mazkur tildagi o'zgarishlar asosida gap tuzilishini ham o'rganishi shart. Ushbu jarayonning ayrim jihatlari ijobiy deb hisoblansa, boshqa tomonlari tashvishga soladi. Punctuatsiya va imlo qoidalariga amal qilmay, noodatiy qisqartmalardan foydalanilishi hamda ularning og'zaki nutqqa o'tib borishi ota-onalar va pedagoglarni o'sib kelayotgan avlod savodxonligiga keskin ta'sir etishi mumkinligi bilan tashvishlantirmoqda. Istalgan chet tili (mazkur holatda - ingliz tili) o'qituvchilari ham bu muammolarning turli qirralari albatta inobatga olinadi, axir bizning ham o'smirlarimiz haqiqiy olamda bo'lgani kabi virtual olamda ham muloqotda bo'lishlari, bilim olishlari va ishlashlariga to'g'ri keladi. Mamlakatimiz mentaliteti, urf-odat va an'analarimiz bolalar ta'lim-tarbiyasida hamda shakllanayotgan shaxslari haqiqiy voqelikka tolerant munosabatda bo'lishlari bilan bunday muammolarning to'g'ri hal etilishiga imkon beradi deb ishonch bilan ayta olamiz. Virtual olamdagi sotsiologik jarayonlarning haqiqiy hayotdagi insonlar muloqotiga ta'siri o'rganishni talab etadigan tilshunoslik muammosi sifatida dolzarflik kasb etmoqda. Elektron kommunikatsiya vositalar tilini hozirgi paytda tilning funksional turi deb hisoblash mumkin. Birinchidan, ushbu til osti tilining qo'llanilish sohasi kommunikatsiyaning boshqa sohalaridan aniq chegaralangan, chunki u texnik elektron vositalar yordamida amalga oshiriladi va doimo ular vositasida ifodalanadi. Ikkinchidan, ushbu til osti tili o'ziga xos kommunikativ maqsadlarni qondirishga xizmat qiladi. Uchinchidan, ushbu til osti tili multimediyaviy janr va shakllarining yangi tizimining yuzaga kelishiga turtki beradi. Tilning asosiy funksiyasi nafaqat axborot yetkazish va undan mustaqil ravishda mavjud bolgan voqe'likka nisbatan tavsif berishdangina iborat emas, balki shaxsning o'ziga xos o'rganish va faoliyat sohasida mo'ljal olishga ko'maklashishdan iboratligi ayon bo'ldi, ya'ni til ko'proq yo'naltiruvchi xulq tizimi sifatida ko'rib chiqila boshlandi. Ushbu yo'nalishning asosiy maqsadi tilning Internetda qo'llanilishining ta'riflash va tushuntirilishidan iborat bo'lishi lozim. Bunda insonning tarmoqdagi muloqotning ijtimoiy-madaniy jihatlari jalb etilganligi sharoitlarda turli omillarning ta'siri mavjudligini inobatga olish kerak.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, agar Internet funksiyalari haqidagi ta'limotga tayangan holda tasavvur qilishga harakat qilsak unda tilning an'anaviy ravishda ajratilib ko'rsatildigan funksiyalari global tarmoqning funksiyalarini ham g'oyatda aniq tavsiflashi ayon boladi.

Dunyo miqyosida sun'iy intellektlar yaratish asosida tabiiy tillarni matematik modellashtirish yotar ekan, matematik modellashtirish natijalari sun'iy intellektning faoliyat dasturini yaratishga asos bo'lib, kompyuter til (yozuv)ini qabul qilishi shart. O'zbek tili amaldagi alifbo va imlo qoidalari bilan internet tili darajasiga ko'tarilgani yo'q. Ma'lumki, amaldagi alifboda 4 ta harf, ya'ni: o', g', ch, sh ni yozish kompyuter klaviaturasida ma'lum tugmalar orqali amalga oshiriladi. Bu esa o'zbek tilining internet tili sifatidagi faoliyatiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. UNICODE tizimida bu grafik shakli mavjud bo'lmaganligi sababli, dasturlashda so'z tarkibida qo'llangan bitta harfning shakli matnidagi so'zlarni bo'lib yuboradi, tavsiya etilayotgan alifbo ushbu muammolarni bartaraf etadi.

Ушбу мақолада ўқув луғатларининг умумий луғатлардан нафақат ҳажми, балки ундаги сўзларнинг танланиш мезонлари, луғат қисмларининг таркиби, жойлашуви – мегаструктураси билан ҳам фарқланиши, синоним ўқув луғатлар луғат мақоласи таркибида лексикографик пометалар (турли қисқартмалар, белгилар)га кам ўрин берилганлиги муҳокама қилинади.¹

This article is dedicated to the research of Adjusted meanings of Moral-spiritual concept defining units in the Uzbek language. And also analyzed the semantic analysis of grammatical shape lexemes of specialized meaning and provide a corresponding recommendation for lexicographical practice in the Uzbek language is one of the actual challenges of linguistics as today's challenge.²

¹ Гуландом Мирханова. (2022). СИНОНИМ СЎЗЛАР ЎҚУВ ЛУҒАТИНИНГ УМУМИЙ ТУЗИЛИШИ. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 172–178. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/90>

² Gulbahor, T. (2016). Adjusted Meanings of Moral-Spiritual Concept Defining Units. *ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies*, 5(7), 40-45.

Корпус лингвистикасида семантик разметка, унинг теглар тизими, тег категориялари, семантик теглаш муаммолари, кўпмаънолилик ва омонимлик муаммосини ечиш масаласига оид қатор тадқиқотлар вужудга келган.³

The article discusses the research methods of Uzbek language syntax. In Uzbek linguistics, syntactic phenomena have been studied in detail since the 1930s, and several syntactic theories have emerged in this regard.⁴

The article examines the first dictionary in the Turkish language Mahmud Kashgaris “Devonu lugotit turk” in terms of a dictionary in accordance with the traditions of world lexicography and argues that it is the first appearance of modern complex dictionaries in the Turkish (Uzbek) language.⁵

Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.⁶

This article covers the main place of small business and business in today's market economy. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal basis, at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added.⁷

Мамлакатимиз тараққиётининг янги босқичида жамият ҳаётининг асосий негизи бўлмиш оилалар барқарор муҳитини мустаҳкамлаш ва бу масалаларда хотин-қизларнинг ўрни ва аҳамияти ошириш долзарб аҳамият касб этмоқда. Юртимиз аҳолисининг тенг

³ Ахмедова, Д. (2020). Семантик разметка тизимида тег гуруҳлари. *Oriental Art and Culture*, (III), 440-444.

⁴ Ergashevna, Y. N. (2021). ON METHODS OF RESEARCH OF UZBEK LANGUAGE SYNTAX. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(11), 22-28.

⁵ Bakhriddinova, B. M. (2020). “DEVONU LUGOTIT TURK” AS A FIRST VIEW OF MODERN COMPLEX EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 981-985.

⁶ Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(05), 211-215.

⁷ Tolibjonovich, Madumarov T., and Gulomjonov O. R. Ogli. "Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 109-111.

ярмига яқинроғини ташкил этадиган хотин-қизлар жамиятнинг барча соҳаларида самарали фаолият юритмоқда.⁸

In this article are given the importance, role, types of the family in modern society. Its development from ancient times till present is widely described in this article.⁹

The widespread introduction of new pedagogical technologies in teaching students of higher educational institutions and the effective use of innovative technologies are the main support for improving the quality of education.¹⁰

The article describes in detail the basics of translation theory, the object of research, and the methods of analysis of translation theory. Opinions on the importance of translation among different peoples, the concept of translation, and its types are discussed. However, various examples of translation types are given.¹¹

The aim of the present study was to determine whether an association exists between the duration of menopause and the age of menopause onset, and the differences in bone mineral density (BMD) in postmenopausal women.¹²

This article analyzes how Somerset Maugham's short story "A Friend in Need" skillfully reflects the power and value of true friendship using ethical concepts such as goodness, kindness, justice, and compassion, which are sacred to each of us.¹³

⁸ Мадумарова Зиёдахон. (2022). ЯНГИЛАНАЁТГАН ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ГЕНДЕР МУАММОЛАРИНИ БАРТАРАФ ЭТИШДА АХЛОҚИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРИНИНГ ЎРНИ. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6569712>

⁹ Nasriddinovich, A. A. (2020). THE FEATURES OF APPEARING FAMILY IN MODERN SOCIETY. *European science review*, (3-4), 69-72.

¹⁰ Jamoliddinovich, U. B. (2022). FUNDAMENTALS OF EDUCATION QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(01), 149-151.

¹¹ Gafurovna, R. Z. (2021). Translation Theory: Object of Research and Methods of Analysis. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 24(2), 35-40.

¹² Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.

¹³ Pulatova Sabina. (2022). THE REVELATION OF VIRTUE THROUGH EVIL IN THE SHORT STORY "A FRIEND IN NEED" BY WILLIAM SOMERSET MAUGHAM. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 240-244. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/100>

The article considers the correlation of the real facts and imagination in “Tamburlaine the Great” by Christopher Marlowe.¹⁴

This article discusses an attitude to women in the past and the interpretation of the image of women in the works of some writers.¹⁵

В современном обществе все более возрастает роль иностранных языков. Знание иностранного языка дает молодежи возможность приобщиться к мировой культуре, использовать в своей деятельности потенциал обширных ресурсов глобальной сети Интернет, а также работать с информационными и коммуникационными технологиями и мультимедийными средствами обучения.¹⁶

This article deals with the heroes of the novel “Between Two Doors”, one of the most popular works of modern Uzbek literature. There is a comprehensive analysis of the female image. A special place in the work of Utkir Khashimov is occupied by the novel “Between Two Doors”. The writer is concerned not only with the pressing social issues of today, but with eternal moral problems. In particular, by calling “Between Two Doors”, the writer means the path of person, which he walked from birth to death.¹⁷

Har bir millat madaniyatida kasallik nomlarini ifodalovchi qarashlar mavjud bo'lib ular shu xalq dunyoqarashini, dinini, urf-odatlarini, turmush tarzini va tarixini o'zida mujassamlashtiradi. Xususan, o'zbek va ingliz xalqi amaliy nutqida rak, sil, vabo kabi xavfli kasalliklar nomi qadimda tabulashtirilgan, bunga tarixiy sabablar mavjud. Hozirgi kunda ularning davosi topilgan bo'lsada, xalqimiz “yomon xastalik”, “og'ir dard”, “yomon kasallik” kabi birikmalarni qo'llash bilan kifoyalanadi.¹⁸

¹⁴ Temirovna, M. P. (2021). THE CORRELATION OF HISTORICAL TRUTH AND IMAGINATION IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S TRAGEDY “TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT”. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(12), 455-457.

¹⁵ Muradovich, R. M. (2021). The Image of a Woman in The Work of Uzbek Writers. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 3, 7-12.

¹⁶ Махмурова, М., Абдуллаева, Л. С., & Самадова, С. А. Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. Коммуникативный метод. *Наука. Мысль*, 6, 72-76.

¹⁷ Turaeva, K., & Zarinabonu, A. (2022). Interpretation Of Woman Image in Modern Uzbek Literature (Based on Utkir Khashimov's Book “Between Two Doors”). *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 4, 42-44.

¹⁸ Baxronova Matluba. (2022). RUHIY KASALLIKLARNING INGLIZ ADABIYOTIDA BERILISHI.

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Badiiy adabiyotning qamrov darajasi keng sanaladi. Zero undagi janrlarning har biri insonning kamoloti uchun xizmat qiladi.¹⁹

В данной статье сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского.²⁰

В настоящее время глобальной социальной опасностью является угроза обнищания населения. Безработица, экономическая и социальная нестабильность, несбыточность надежд, крушение планов интенсифицируют процесс маргинализация населения.²¹

The relevance of speech and culture in the present day is considered important in linguistics and its areas of study are becoming more and more comprehensive day by day. This article will highlight the important aspects of the study of culture and national characteristics in the study of modern units of oral speech. Currently, English is widely spoken in the world community. It is the language of Advanced Science and technology, trade and cultural relations, trade and business.²²

The article is dedicated to the description of Uzbek national children's clothes of the past centuries and its modern implementation. Article describes types of clothes, its designation and modern usage.²³

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR:

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¹⁹ Oripova Kamola. (2022). O'ZBEK VA FRANSUZ TILLARIDAGI MAQOLLARDA JON KONSEPTINING IFODALANISHI. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(3), 398–408. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/209>

²⁰ Тухтаева, Ф. И., & Хамроева, Ш. Ш. (2019). Сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского. *Мировая наука*, (5), 709-713.

²¹ Суяров, З. Э. (2021). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКОЕ ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ БЕДНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(12), 1175-1182.

²² NARZIYEVA, I. Z. (2021, March). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND NATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MODERN UNITS OF ORAL SPEECH (based on Uzbek and English language materials). In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 285-289).

²³ Kadirova, N. A. (2020). UZBEK NATIONAL CHILDRENS CLOTHING AND ITS EVOLUTION. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (6), 155-157.

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